

Questions to RISE

Interview with Anneli Hellström

In RISE is responsible for the case study related to forestry. What is your impression about current challenges related to certification?

In dialogue with BioReCer stakeholders, it is clear that there are a few challenges and improvement opportunities in the sector related to certification and gaps in the current systems. One clear example is the discrepancy between the percentage of certified forest biomass and that of forest biomass which fulfil the certification criteria but is not certified. Whereas they are equally good from a sustainability perspective, the latter is discriminated in today's framework, and the administrative burden can be a hinder for small and/or private actors, which are numerous in the forest sector.

Which forestry sector actors are involved in the BIORECER certification chain of custody?

The forest sector chain of custody varies: for some products, the same actor plays multiple roles, i.e. is both primary, intermediate and final producer, whereas for other products, different actors are present in the value chain. Among the actors, there are forest owners, sawmills, pulp mills and biorefineries. Several companies are both forest owners, have their own sawmills and pulp mills and either refine their residual streams themselves or sell them to another partner, who does the refinement.

What type of forestry-specific data (WP2) is being used in the study? Is it data related to biomass, species types, residue volumes, or something else?

Various data is used in the study: masses of primary and main products like lumber, sawlogs and pulpwood, residual streams like bark, sawdust and woodchips. Furthermore, energy and chemical inputs are also considered.